

THE PROBLEM OF LEARNING ENGLISH AND THEIR SOLUTION

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Abstract: *The problem that arises when learning English and its solution. Perhaps you have already encountered similar difficulties more than once.*

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Learning languages has its ups and downs. Sometimes you progress really fast, but sometimes there is a feeling of "standing still". Don't worry, it's normal. The learning process is very similar to sports. There are also plateau phases where you don't move forward in your results. But if you are constantly learning, you will improve anyway. In this article, you will learn about the most common language learning problems and how to solve them.

I understand speech very well but I can't speak

This is a problem that often occurs in people who have been studying a language in school for many years or in language courses. But it can also happen if you devote a lot of time to learning the language, but speak little yourself.

Solution : Talk as much as possible Look for native speakers with whom you can talk about a variety of topics .Think in the language regularly and try to talk to

yourself. You will notice that your language skills are improving rapidly and you will see results in just a few weeks.

I can talk, but I can't understand other people's speech.

If you have this problem, then this is quite normal. This is a natural development in language learning, because it is easier to formulate a thought in a foreign language than to understand the rapid colloquial speech of a native speaker. Plus, it can be very difficult to understand all the possible phrase combinations that are used in a conversation. Keep up the good work and communicate more with native speakers . Also, try to improve your listening skills. Listen as much as possible in a foreign language. You can do this with podcasts , audiobooks , movies , series , music, et.c.

Watching programs with subtitles in a foreign language works great.

I keep forgetting words.

more words you try to learn, the harder it is to keep them in your memory. This problem excites absolutely all beginners! Especially if you don't use the dictionary often enough, or at least don't repeat the learned words regularly.

Solution : speak the language and use many different words , especially new ones . Write down words that are important to you but that you often forget. Try to build them into the conversation, using them in different contexts. Don't have anyone to talk to? Tell yourself an entertaining story. Another option is to try using word cards.

My accent is too strong, you feel that your accent is too.

Do you feel like your accent is too strong and other people don't understand you? This may be because you started learning the language at a later age. Also, do not forget that in a foreign language there are letters and sounds that do not exist in Russian. In English , for example , " th " (the words " the >> and " that ") .

Solution: Talk to native speakers and try to correct your pronunciation. Pay close attention to how they speak and try to imitate their speech. There are many videos on the Internet that show you how to pronounce sounds and words correctly. If all this does not help, then you can always consult our teachers.

I'm afraid of making mistakes. He who doesn't make mistakes doesn't develop. It's an axiom!

Solution: You must constantly use the language and try to make new sentences and grammatical constructions to improve your skills. Language tandems are very useful. You practice a foreign language and your partner is Russian. It is best to look for a partner who has the same level of Russian language proficiency as you do in foreign language. You will feel much calmer when you personally see that your partner, like you, makes a lot of mistakes and has constant difficulties in learning the language.

My speech is worse than before This can happen if you don't use the language for a long time.

Sometimes this can happen after a few weeks off.

Solution : Just keep talking and you will notice that you quickly returned to the previous results.

I confuse different foreign languages This happens when you learn two very similar languages, such as Spanish and French.

However, this can often happen when you study a language intensively for one day, and in the evening switch to another language that you are not fluent in. On the machine, you always remember words from another language.

Solution : If you sleep soundly at night you will usually not have problems switching to another language. Talking in another language for 5-10 minutes is enough to switch to another language. This is also the reason why it is not

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recommended to study several languages at the same time. It is better to focus on one language and study it until you can speak it fluently. And then start learning a new language which makes your life very difficult. Consider what words and grammatical structures you already know, and keep it as simple as possible - don't immediately try to speak in florid phrases. Try to use to the maximum the arsenal of words that you already know well. remember that everyone makes mistakes. One student from the practice of our teacher stopped being afraid when he realized that his business partner from Germany also had far from perfect English. There are two types of conversational tasks in textbooks - for accuracy and for fluency. To overcome the language barrier, you need the second type.

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